

Master Reference List: Academic & Legal Formatting

Category	Resource Name & Description	Format	Source
Legal Writing	Law Memo & IRAC Checklist	PDF	Columbia Law
Legal Writing	Academic Bluebook Footnote Guide	PDF	Georgetown Law
Thesis Style	Graduate Thesis Formatting Checklist	PDF	U-Minnesota
Thesis Style	Long-Form Manuscript Layout Guide	PDF	Montclair State
APA Style	Official APA 7th Ed. Student Setup	PDF	APA.org
APA Style	Annotated APA Sample Paper	Web	Purdue OWL
MLA Style	MLA General Formatting Cheat Sheet	PDF	Wayland Baptist
General	Multi-Style Citation Comparison Chart	PDF	Purdue OWL